

Isolation and characterization of coumarin derivatives from methanolic extract of *Cressa cretica* Linn.

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Abstract : The methanolic extract of the fruits of *Cressa cretica* Linn. gave β -sitosterol, 6-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin and 6-methoxy-7,8-methylenedioxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin. These were characterized on the basis of spectroscopic studies.

Keywords : *Cressa cretica* Linn., sterol, coumarins.

Introduction

Cressa cretica Linn. (Convolvulaceae) is known in India as Rudanti. It is reported to be antibilious, antitubercular and expectorant¹. The plant is alternatively used as an anthelmintic, stomachic, tonic for aphrodisiac purposes, for enrichment of the blood, constipation, leprosy, asthma, urinary discharges and general debility². Dry leaves of *Cressa cretica* Linn. mixed with sugar are used as emetic³. Flavonoids from this plant produce antiandrogenic activity and affect fertility in male dogs^{4,5}. The plant is used as antibacterial^{6,7}, antifungal⁸, antifertility⁹, antitussive¹⁰, anticancer¹¹, antitubercular and antimicrobial¹².

Phytochemical screening of the plant revealed the presence of alkaloids, coumarins, sterols¹³, flavonoids, quercetin, quercetin-3-O-glucoside, kampferol-3-rhamnoglucoside, rutin¹⁴, syringaresinol- β -D-glucoside, scopoletin, 3,5-dicaffeoylquinic acid, 4,5-dicaffeoylquinic acid¹⁵, creticane, cressatetracosanoate, cressanonacontanoic acid, cressatetriacontanoic acid, cressatriacontanone and cressanaphthacenone¹⁶ which showed pharmaceutical activities. Significant medicinal properties attributed to this plant prompted us to take up its phytochemical investigation. We herein report the isolation and characterization of β -sitosterol (1), 6-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (2) and 6-methoxy-7,8-methylenedioxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (3) from its fruits. 6-Hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (2) and 6-methoxy-7,8-methylenedioxy-

coumarin (3) were reported for the first time from this plant.

Results and discussion

6-Hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (2), m.p. 241–243 °C, was found to be homogeneous on TLC. The elemental analysis and molecular weight determination indicated its molecular formula as C₁₁H₁₀O₃. The appearance of blue green colour in UV light indicated its coumarin nature¹⁷. The important peaks observed in the infrared spectrum were at 3500 (OH stretching), 1720 (coumarin lactone), 1615, 1560, 1570 (aromatic C=C) and 1130 cm⁻¹ (O=C-O). In the ¹H NMR spectrum, the presence of three protons were observed in the aromatic region. A doublet at δ 6.77 (*J* 8.0 Hz) corresponded to C-8 proton which was *ortho*-coupled to C-7 proton which appeared as a doublet at δ 7.27 (*J* 8.0, 2.0 Hz). The third aromatic proton (C-5) was observed as a doublet at δ 7.33 (*J* 2.0 Hz) which was placed *meta* to C-7 proton. In addition to this, two methyl singlets appeared at δ 2.15 and 2.35 which could be placed at C-3 and C-4, respectively. In the mass spectrum, the molecular ion-peak was observed at *m/z* 190, which was also the base peak. Prominent peaks appeared at *m/z* 175 [M-CH₃]⁺, 162 [M-CO]⁺ and 134 [M-2CO]⁺. From these spectral data the structure of the compound was established as 6-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (2) (Reported¹⁸, m.p. 241 °C). This is the first report of the isolation and characterization of 6-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin from *Cressa cretica*.

6-Methoxy-7,8-methylenedioxy coumarin (**3**), m.p. 219–221 °C, was found to be homogenous on TLC. The elemental analysis and molecular weight determination indicated its molecular formula as $C_{11}H_8O_5$. The positive Labat test¹⁹ and colour with acidified phloroglucinol indicated the presence of a methylenedioxy group. In the UV spectrum, absorption at λ_{max} 330, 259 and 213 nm and blue fluorescence in UV light indicated its coumarin nature. The important peaks observed in the infrared spectrum were at 1720 (C=O), 1620, 1590, 1550 (aromatic C=C) and 1130 cm^{-1} (O=C-O). The 1H NMR spectrum exhibited signals due to three aromatic protons appearing as two doublets at δ 7.57 (d, J 9.6 Hz) and 6.27 (d, J 9.6 Hz) for protons attached to C-4 and C-3 atoms respectively and a singlet at δ 6.58 for C-5 proton. Besides these, a three-proton singlet at δ 3.93 and a two-proton singlet at δ 6.16 corresponded to the presence of a methoxy and a methylenedioxy group in the compound. In the mass spectrum, the molecular ion-peak was observed at m/z 220. Prominent peak also appeared at m/z 205 [M-15]⁺, 192 [M-28]⁺ and 177. These physical and spectral data closely resembled those of 6-methoxy-7,8-methylenedioxy coumarin (Reported²⁰, m.p. 219–221 °C). On the basis of above discussion, the structure for the compound was determined as 6-methoxy-7,8-methylenedioxy coumarin (**3**).

The characterization of β -sitosterol (**1**) was established on the basis of mixed m.p. and Co-TLC with an authentic sample and comparison of spectral data with those reported in literature²¹.

Experimental

General : Melting points were determined in soft glass capillaries in an electrothermal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Column chromatography was performed on silica gel (60–120 mesh) and TLC on Merck's silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ precoated glass plates. The FT-IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellet on a NICOLET MEGNA FT-IR 550 spectrophotometer. The 1H NMR spectra were recorded in $CDCl_3$ at 300 MHz on a Bruker NMR instrument using TMS as internal standard. EI mass spectra were recorded on JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer using Argon/Xenon as gas. The spots on TLC were visualized with 1% ceric sulphate in 2 N H_2SO_4 as spray reagent.

Plant material : The fruits of the plant were collected from Ramgarh Dame, Jaipur, Rajasthan (India) and authenticated by Mr. Roop Singh, In-charge of Herbarium, Department of Botany, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur.

Extraction : Shade-dried fruits (2.0 kg) were powdered and extracted with methanol on steam bath for 72 h. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and the resulting dark green, semi-solid mass was chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh) to obtain three fractions. Fraction 1 (chloroform : benzene, 1 : 1) gave β -sitosterol as yellowish crystalline solid, 435 mg, m.p. 136–137 °C. Fraction 2 (chloroform : ethyl acetate, 3 : 1) yielded 6-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (**2**) as shining green crystals, 86 mg, m.p. 241–243 °C. Fraction 3 (chloroform : ethyl acetate, 1 : 3) afforded 6-methoxy-7,8-methylenedioxy coumarin (**3**) as colourless crystals, 36 mg, m.p. 219–221 °C.

Spectral data : 6-Hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (**2**), m.p. 241–243 °C; IR (cm^{-1} , KBr) : 3500, 1720, 1615, 1570, 1560, 1130, 690; 1H NMR : 57.33 (1H, d, H-5), 7.27 (1H, dd, H-7), 6.77 (1H, d, H-8), 2.35 (3H, s, 4- CH_3), 2.15 (3H, s, 3- CH_3); MS (EI, 70 eV) : 190 [M⁺], 175, 162, 161, 134, 133, 108, 107, 90, 84 (Found : C, 69.43; H, 5.26. Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$: C, 69.38; H, 5.25%).

6-Methoxy-7,8-methylenedioxy coumarin (**3**), m.p. 219–221 °C; IR (cm^{-1} , KBr) : 1720, 1620, 1590, 1560, 1130, 655; 1H NMR : 57.57 (1H, d), 7.51 (1H, d), 6.58 (1H, s), 6.30 (2H, s, -O- CH_2 -O-), 6.16 (3H, s, -O CH_3), 3.93

(3H, s, -OCH₃); MS (EI, 70 eV) : 220 [M⁺], 205, 204, 192, 177, 146, 134, 120, 106, 91, 79, 69 (Found : C, 60.07; H, 3.63. Calcd. for C₁₁H₈O₅ : C, 60.03; H, 3.62%).

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